

Developer User Story Analysis - RDA Minimal MD

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Developer wanting to add to or create web interface (US 9) Developer wanting to import metadata into a different catalog (US 11) Developer looking to reuse data about OER objects for different application (US 16)				
2	Generic Term	Description	Metadata req	Useful for Extended Doc	Comment / Notes
3	title	The name of the resource.	Y	Y	
4	abstract	A brief overview of the item (container)	Y	Y	
5	abstract_data	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	Y	Y	
6	access_cost	Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (Boolean).	Y	Y	
7	author(s)	List of full name of the author(s)	Y	Y	All info related to the authorship of a given learning resource are very important for a developer that wants to reuse that specific resource in order to correctly cite the source.
8	author.familyName	Last or family name of person(s) authoring the resource.	Y	Y	
9	author.givenName	First or given name of person(s) authoring the resource	Y	Y	
10	author_org	Name of organization authoring the resource.	Y	Y	
11	contributor(s)	List of full name of secondary person(s) contributing to the resource.	Recmnd	Y	
12	contributor_orgs.name	Name of contributing organization(s)	Recmnd	Y	
13	contributor_orgs.type	Type of contribution made by the organization	Recmnd	Y	
14	contributors.familyName	Family or last name of the contributor.	Recmnd	Y	
15	contributors.givenName	Given or first name of contributor(s)	Recmnd	Y	
16	name_identifier	The unique identifier for individual or organization referenced.	Recmnd	Y	
17	name_type	The name of the identifier scheme.	Recmnd	Y	
18	contributors.type	Type of contribution made by a person or organization.	Recmnd	Y	
19	contribution_date	Date of the contribution to the resource	N	N	
20	contribution_entity	Identification of and information about entities (i.e., people, organizations) contributing to the resource	N	N	
21	language_primary	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	Y	Y	
22	languages_secondary	Additional languages in which the resource is available, if any.	Recmnd	Y	
23	keywords	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	Y	Y	
24	license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	Y	Y	Very important
25	lr_type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	Y	Y	
26	target_audience	Principle users(s) for which the resource was designed.	Recmnd	Y	

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27	subject	Subject domain toward which the resource is targeted.	Optional	Recmnd	
28	skill_level	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate, advanced.	Recmnd	Y	Highly Recmnd (very relevant in order to automatically select learning resourcers for a specific skill leven on a given topic)
29	typical_age_range	The typical range of ages for the content's intended end user.	N	N	
30	difficulty	How hard it is to work with or through the resource for the typical intended target audience (very easy, easy, medium, difficult, very difficult, knowledge-dependent)	N	N	The difficulty is something subjective since it depends on the basic knowledge that a user has on the specific topic
31	published	Date of publication / broadcast.	Y	Y	
32	modification_date	Date at which the educational resource was most recently published or broadcast.	Y	Y	
33	version	The specific version of the resource, if declared.	Y	Y	Very important to import metadata into a different catalog. Developer can decide if taking only the last version of a given LR or all its versions
34	publisher	The organization credited with publishing or broadcasting the resource (does not include the repository where resource is stored).	Y	Y	
35	url	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	Y	Y	
36	usage_info	Text describing information about using the resource, not addressed by the license URL.	Y	Y	
37	usage_restrictions	Yes / No response to whether copyright or other restrictions apply to the use of the resource	Recmnd	Recmnd	If no other info is available about copyright or licensing, could use this.
38	use_rights_url	The URL where the owner specifies permissions for using the resource	Y	Y	If no other info is available about copyright or licensing, should use this as some information is required for FAIR at least.
39	learning_outcome	Descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	Recmnd	Y	
40	citation	Preferred form of citation	Recmnd	Recmnd	
41	locator.data	From DC "An unambiguous reference to the resources within a given context." Use a string that conforms to an ID system. See how FAIRsFAIR deals with this...	Optional	Recmnd	

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42	locator.type	Controlled vocabulary designating the persistent identifier schemes used for the resource, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	Optional	Recmnd	
43	completion_time	Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through the resource for the typical, intended target audience.	Recmnd	Recmnd	
44	completion_status	Completion status or condition of the resource (draft, final, revised, unavailable)	Recmnd	Recmnd	
45	interactivity_level	Degree of interactivity characterizing the resource; refers to the degree to which the learner can influence the aspect of behavior of resource (e.g., very low, low, medium, high, very high).	Optional	Recmnd	
46	interactivity_type	The predominant mode of learning supported by the learning resource (i.e., active, expositive, or mixed)	Recmnd	Recmnd	
47	credential_status	Type of credentialing offered for the resource, if any.	Recmnd	Y	
48	contact	Name of person who has been asserted as the contact(s) for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	Recmnd	Recmnd	
49	email	Email address of person or organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource.	Recmnd	Recmnd	
50	org	Name of organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	Recmnd	Recmnd	
51	media_type	From schema.org def: "Media type of resource, typically expressed using a MIME format" from IANA site & MDN reference.	N	Recmnd	
52	ed_frameworks.name	The name of an framework to which the resource is aligned, if any.	Optional	Optional	
53	ed_frameworks.nodes.description	The description of a node in an educational framework	Optional	Optional	
54	ed_frameworks.nodes.name	The name of a node in an established educational framework.	Optional	Optional	
55	ed_frameworks.nodes.url	The URL of a node in an established educational framework.	Optional	Optional	
56	ed_frameworks.url	The URL of an established educational framework	Optional	Optional	
57	alignment_type	A category of alignment between the learning resource and the framework node. (See notes for Recmnd values).	Optional	Y	
58	hasPart	A sub-Training resource or externally referenced resource	Recmnd	Recmnd	
59	isPartOf	Course in which this resource was/will be used, or the resource in which this resource is a part (e.g., part of a book or slide-set associated with a course).	Recmnd	Recmnd	With these metadata developers can understand if the specific LR has been already created by reusing an existing one
60	is_based_on_url	A resource that was used in the creation of this resource (repeatable)	Recmnd	Recmnd	

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61	resource_size	Size of the resource in bytes (uncompressed)	Recmnd	Recmnd	Very important if applicable (downloadable resources)
62	accessibility_control	Indicates input methods that are sufficient to fully control the described resource (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	
63	accessibility_features	Content features of the resource, such as accessible media, alternatives and supported enhancements for accessibility (WebSchemas wiki lists possible values). Only 4 values of the entire list were available in the drupal production system; others are to be added to the CV for this field as called for.	N	Optional	
64	accessibility_hazard	A characteristic of the described resource that is physiologically dangerous to some users. (CV list of values at: https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	
65	accessibility_summary	Human readable summary of accessibility features and deficiencies	N	Optional	
66	accessibility_api	Indicates that the resource is compatible with the referenced accessibility API (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	
67	date_created	The date on which the resource was created.	Recmnd	Recmnd	It could be an relevant aspect for a developer who is willing to reuse that specifi LR
68	country_of_origin	Code for country from which resource was generated;	N	Optional	
69	coverage	Time, culture, geography or region to which this learning object applies. The extent or scope of its content. Coverage will typically include spatial location (a place name or geographic coordinates), temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administratie entity).	N	Optional	
70	mentions	Data-sets, tools, technologies, entities, other training materials in the series, etc., to which the resource makes reference. **	N	Optional	
71	context	Principal environment within which the learning & use of the resource is intended to take place, e.g., school, higher education, etc.	N	Optional	
72	purpose	The purpose of the work in the context of education.	N	N	Ambiguous term
73	uses	Data-sets, tools, technolgies, entites, etc. that are actively utilised in this resource.	N	Optional	

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74	rating	Placeholder for comments given by users assessing the educational resource after use.	N	Optional	
75	ratings	If applicable, placeholder for overall ratings for the educational resource, based on a collection of reviews or ratings.	N	Optional	
76	semantic_density	Degree of conciseness; may be estimated in terms of its size, span or duration	N	Optional	Related to interactivity level. May be difficult to discern.
77	System MD fields below:				
78	id	System identifier for the MD record.	Y	Y	System field
79	md_record_id	Globally unique, persistent ID for the metadata record within the system for the resource being described.	Y	Y	Necessary for FAIR; should be in the form of a resolvable ID, e.g., DOI, Handle, ARK, LSID, etc.
80	submitter_email	Person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N.A.	N.A.	Not necessary for discovery; useful for admin/system
81	submitter_name	Email address of person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N.A.	N.A.	Not necessary for discovery; useful for admin/system
82	created	The date on which the metadata record was created.	N.A.	N.A.	System field
83	creator	The login name of the person creating the MD record.	N.A.	N.A.	System field
84	featured_event	Course instance or event where this training resource was or will be featured. (inverse of workFeatured)	N.A.	N.A.	Events out of scope.
85					
86	resource_id_label	A globally unique label that identifies the learning object.	?	?	Used by ENVRI LOM: identifier (General 1.1)
87	resource_id_scheme	Name or designator of the identification or cataloging scheme for the globally unique label (resource ID)	?	?	Used by ENVRI LOM: catalog (General 1.2)
88	resource_id_value	Value of the identifier within the identification or cataloging scheme that designates or identifies the learning object. Should be a namespace specific string.	?	?	Used by ENVRI LOM: entry (General 1.3)
89					
90	REFERENCES				
91	* Taken from https://zenodo.org/record/3903341 (ENVRI LOM profile)				
92	** Taken from https://bioschemas.org/profiles/TrainingMaterial/0.7-DRAFT-2019_11_08/				
93					